

THE ABUNDANCE OF OLIGOTROPHS IN THE HYDROMORPHIC SOILS OF THE MIRZACHUL OASIS

Kodirova Dilrabo Abdukarimovna
Rahimov Zarqum Zafarjonzoda

Doctor of Biological Sciences, Professor, Tashkent State Agrarian University
²PhD student at Gulistan State University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17907268>

Abstract. This article presents the seasonal dynamics and quantitative distribution of oligotrophic microorganisms in irrigated meadow-alluvial soils of the “Mustaqillik” massif located in the Mirzaobod district of Syrdarya region. The study analyzes oligotroph abundance across different genetic horizons and soil salinity levels under various crop types.

Keywords: oligotrophs, CFU/g, seasonal dynamics, soil salinity, irrigated soils, microbial abundance, soil profile.

Introduction

These microorganisms are adapted to nutrient-poor environments and are capable of growing by utilizing minimal nutrient sources. They play an important role in maintaining soil fertility and in enhancing the efficient uptake of nutrients by plants. The abundance of oligotrophs in soil varies significantly depending on the crop type, the degree of salinity, the depth of the soil profile, and seasonal fluctuations.

Obtained Results and Their Analysis

According to the results of chemical analysis, the abundance of oligotrophic microorganisms in Profile 1 reached $4,9 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in the 0–33 cm soil layer in spring, $1,5 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in summer, and $1,8 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in autumn. In the 33–56 cm layer, their number was $3,0 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in spring, $1,2 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in summer, and $1,3 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in autumn.

In Profile 24, the oligotroph count in the 0–32 cm layer amounted to $7,5 \times 10^4$ CFU/g in spring, $3,1 \times 10^4$ CFU/g in summer, and $4,7 \times 10^4$ CFU/g in autumn. In the deeper 32–55 cm layer, their abundance was $3,0 \times 10^4$ CFU/g in spring, $2,2 \times 10^4$ CFU/g in summer, and $2,5 \times 10^4$ CFU/g in autumn.

In Profile 29, these microorganisms reached $2,4 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in spring within the 0–29 cm layer, $1,4 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in summer, and $1,6 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in autumn. In the 29–53 cm layer, their number varied between $1,5 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in spring, $9,3 \times 10^4$ CFU/g in summer, and $1,2 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in autumn.

Table 1.

Seasonal indices of oligotrophs in soils, CFU/g
(colony-forming units per 1 g of soil)

Profile No.	Layer depth, cm	Crop type	Salinity level	Seasons of the year		
				Spring	Summer	Autumn
1	0-33	Alfalfa	slightly saline	$4,9 \times 10^5$	$1,5 \times 10^5$	$1,8 \times 10^5$
	33-56		slightly saline	3×10^5	$1,2 \times 10^5$	$1,3 \times 10^5$
24	0-32	Wheat	moderately saline	$7,5 \times 10^4$	$3,1 \times 10^4$	$4,7 \times 10^4$
	32-55		highly saline	3×10^4	$2,2 \times 10^4$	$2,5 \times 10^4$
29	0-29	Melon	slightly saline	$2,4 \times 10^5$	$1,4 \times 10^5$	$1,6 \times 10^5$
	29-53		slightly saline	$1,5 \times 10^5$	$9,3 \times 10^4$	$1,2 \times 10^5$
68	0-31	Corn	non-saline	$5,6 \times 10^5$	2×10^5	$2,2 \times 10^5$
	31-52		non-saline	$2,5 \times 10^5$	$1,3 \times 10^5$	$1,7 \times 10^5$

In the 68th soil profile, the amount of oligotrophic microorganisms in the 0–31 cm layer reached $5,6 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in spring, $2,0 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in summer, and $2,2 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in autumn, whereas in the subsurface plow layer (31–52 cm), their abundance amounted to $2,5 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in spring, $1,3 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in summer, and $1,7 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in autumn (Table 1).

The amount of oligotrophic microorganisms in the soils of the studied area varies significantly depending on soil depth, salinity level, and seasonal changes. According to the research findings, the highest values of oligotrophs were recorded in non-saline and slightly saline soils, particularly in the plow layer during the spring season. This is associated with relatively favorable conditions such as higher moisture, improved aeration, and better nutrient availability.

As the degree of salinity increases, the number of oligotrophs decreases, reaching minimal levels in highly saline soils. In terms of seasonal dynamics, microbial activity is highest in spring, decreases in summer due to high temperatures and moisture deficit, and shows partial recovery in autumn.

Figure 1. Quantity of oligotrophs in soils

Conclusions

In summary, the abundance of microorganisms, including oligotrophs, is generally higher in the plow layer. This can be explained by the greater accumulation of organic matter, better aeration, and optimal moisture distribution in this layer. In the subsurface layer, microbial density is relatively lower due to limited nutrient availability, oxygen deficiency, higher soil compaction, and fluctuating hydrothermal conditions.

Overall, oligotrophic microorganisms are one of the key components indicating soil biological activity. Their ability to survive in nutrient-poor environments makes them essential contributors to maintaining soil ecological stability.

References:

1. Zvyagintsev, D.G. *Methods of Soil Microbiology and Biochemistry*. Moscow: Moscow State University, 1991. 224 p.
2. Kazeev, K.Sh., Kolesnikov, S.I., Valkov, V.F. *Soil Biology of Southern Russia*. Rostov-on-Don: Publishing House, 2004. 350 p.
3. Valkov, V.F., Kolesnikov, S.I., Kazeev, K.Sh. *Methodology for Studying Soil Biological Activity (Using the Example of the North Caucasus)* // *Scientific Thought of the Caucasus*. 1999. No. 1. P. 32–37.

4. Babaev, M.P., Orudzheva, N.I. Assessment of Biological Activity in the Subtropical Zone of Azerbaijan // Eurasian Soil Science. 2009. No. 10. P. 1248–1255.

